

Specificities of post-Islamism in Tunisia and Iran: the cases of Harakat Ennahda and the neo-Shariati movement

Islam and democracy: from Islamism to post-Islamism

The debate on Islam and democracy has been a leitmotiv of the discourse on Islamism since the birth of this ideology. Due to the high degree of diversity within the Muslim world, differing views have emerged regarding the compatibility between Islam and democracy, or its absence, among Muslim and Western scholars. Thus, the discourse on Islam and democracy is polarized between those who purport their compatibility and those who do not. The latter affirm that democracy is a Western ‘imported solution’, and it cannot and should not be reconciliated with the Islamic values. This branch of thought paved the way for radical Islamism, which at times degenerated in violent expressions, as has happened, among other scenarios, in Algeria or Egypt¹. On the other hand, those who support the compatibility between Islam and democracy did so on the basis of their understanding of Islamic law, driving their willingness to actively participate in the political life of their countries. In the last decades, especially after the Green Movement (2009) and the Arab Springs (2011), this topic has gained more traction thanks to the predominance of Islamist movements in politics and society. This process has led to the reformulation of the Islamist ideology, which can legitimately be understood as a process of post-Islamization, where there is a shift from the focus on the strict interpretation of sacred texts to a holistic approach based on values and rights. Therefore, Islamism and post-Islamism are the key to understanding not only past events, but the possible evolutions of the Muslim political world as well.

Islamism is, in short, the “instrumentalization of religion to pursue political objectives”, these being mainly the creation of an Islamic system (*nizam islami*), which would present itself as an Islamic state (*dawla islami*) based on the implementation of sharia and the Quranic principle of encouraging good and forbidding wrong². Of course, Islamism as a concept has been read and explained extensively in different ways, mostly as a continuation of anti-colonialism and a response to the uncertainty of the post-modern world³. As a phenomenon, it has taken various forms ranging from revolutionary regime

¹ Esposito and Voll, *Islam and democracy*, 11-51; Tibi, *Islamism and Islam*, 31-53; Lewis, “Islam and Liberal Democracy”, 52-63.

² Denoëux, “The Forgotten Swamp”, 61; Bayat, *Post-Islamism*, 4-5.

³ Kepel, *The Revenge of God*, passim; Burgat and Dowell, *The Islamic Movements in North Africa*, passim; Shahin, “Secularism and Nationalism”, passim; Esposito, *Political Islam*, 1-16

changes (mainly the Iranian Revolution of 1979) to violence, in the form of jihadi terrorist groups which base their understanding of the concept on a strict adoption of Sayyid Qutb's ideology⁴.

During the Nineties, the development and the fall of Islamist movements led to a rethinking of the phenomenon of Islamism *per se*, thanks to the renovated understanding of democracy in MENA countries. Hence, the question on whether Islam was compatible with democracy inevitably arose and led to the birth of the so-called post-Islamist current. The term post-Islamism was introduced by Asef Bayat to describe the 'metamorphosis of Islamism', and was then widened mainly by Bayat himself, Olivier Roy and Gilles Kepel⁵. Therefore, similarly to Islamism, post-Islamism has different shades, and it can be understood as a complex framework. For instance, Roy considers post-Islamism in global terms, focusing on the failure of the Islamist design worldwide and tracing the shift from a radical political Islamic discourse to a more moderate Islamist agenda⁶. On the other hand, Kepel's understanding of post-Islamism can be included in the broader phenomenon of the de-globalization of Islam. He focused in particular on the parallel evolution of globalization and the response of Islamic political parties and movements to the globalized world, shedding light on the changing relationship between Islam and democratic institutions⁷. However, according to Bayat, Roy and Kepel's definitions are more empirical than analytical since they are limited to the description of the evolution of Islamism or Islamization itself in a specific period of time⁸. In that sense, Bayat's description of post-Islamism seems to be more nuanced, because he also considered this phenomenon as an attempt to overturn the rationale of Islamism by focusing on plurality and human rights through an historical contextualization of Islam. This framework is opposed to the Islamist strict transposition and interpretation of sharia, in particular in its legal application in everyday life, that inevitably entails ahistorical duties upon the individual rather than rights. Post-Islamism is then both 'a condition and a project' that transcends the debate on whether Islam can be democratized or democracy can be Islamized, and it represents the merger of modernity and Islam⁹.

Bayat's definition of post-Islamism as an analytical tool not only allows for the study of the developments of MENA region taking into account the individual features of each country, but also gives the opportunity to compare different experiences in order to highlight similarities or differences in specific contexts. In that sense, the cases of Harakat Ennahda in Tunisia until 2016 and the neo-Shariati movement in Iran until 2009 embody two declinations of post-Islamism in two starkly

⁴ Kepel, *Uscire dal caos*, 24-26, 96-97; Campanini, *La politica nell'Islam*, 221, 246; Maggiolini, "Ĝihād e jihadismo", 201.

⁵ Bayat, "What Is Post-Islamism?", 5.

⁶ Roy, *The Failure of Political Islam*, 28-34; Roy, "Le post-islamisme", 9-30; Roy, *Globalized Islam*, 58-97.

⁷ Kepel, "Islamism Reconsidered", 22-27; Kepel, *Jihad*, 414-416.

⁸ Bayat, "What Is Post-Islamism?", 5; Mahdavi, "Post-Islamist Trends", 95.

⁹ Bayat, "Post-Islamism", 3-33; Bayat, *Making Islam Democratic*, 1-15.

different countries. Even if those experiences differ due to history, culture and language, they broadly share religion even if with different denominations, namely Sunnism and Shiism. Therefore, the general principles of Islam are accepted among both Tunisia and Iran, and sharing those principles paved the way for the evolution of the Islamist movements of these countries toward peculiar forms of post-Islamism. As a matter of fact, whereas Ennahda coined for itself the label of ‘Muslim Democracy’, the neo-Shariati movement developed a particular understanding of secular democracy, in an attempt to free religion from politics, and thus they are worthy of being compared in order to shed light on their similarities and differences.

Ennahda: from pious movement to political party

Ennahda was founded in the early Seventies as a pious movement called Al-Jama’ah Al-Islamiyyah. Its founders, namely Rachid Ghannouchi and Abdel Fattah Al-Mouru, had met in the late Sixties through the state backed Association pour la Sauvegarde du Coran, as they had turned to Islam in search for a solution to the socioeconomic issues Tunisia was facing at the time. In particular the catastrophic failure of the socialist experiment, and Bourguiba’s nonchalant and sudden turn to liberalism, had caused a dramatic increase in unemployment, especially among the educated youth, who found themselves perplexed in regard to the country’s future¹⁰.

In its infancy the Jama’ah’s position, diffused through Al-Ma’rifah, its journal, was critical of the West’s decadence and its influence on Tunisia, as opposed to Islam, which the Jama’ah proposed as the only cure to such moral and social decadence. Furthermore, thanks to Sadat’s reconciliation with the Muslim Brotherhood in Egypt, which allowed it to openly produce literature, the Brotherhood’s ideology flooded the Middle East, influencing in turn the Jama’ah, though the Tunisian Islamists were not yet fully politicized¹¹.

A first foray into politics took place in 1978, after the brutal governmental repressions of the strikes of the so-called *Jeudi Noir* (January 26th). However, the Jama’ah did not place the blame for the bloodshed at the feet of Bourguiba’s government, but rather at those of the Tunisian Marxist movement. Indeed, the Jama’ah interpreted the event as an attempt by the left to put in place a communist revolution, with the intent to strip Tunisia of its Arabic and Islamic aspects¹². The clash with the Marxists had already taken place in the campuses, where the Islamist students had opposed the left, in turn becoming themselves more politicized, and critical of the upper echelon of the

¹⁰ Tamburini, *Il Maghreb*, 370-371.

¹¹ Burgat, *Il fondamentalismo islamico*, 166-168.

¹² Burgat, *Il fondamentalismo islamico*, 175-176.

Jama'ah, whom, focusing exclusively on its moral pursuits, had not given them the political tools to face their leftist opponents¹³.

But in the end the turning point for the Jama'ah was the Iranian revolution. Indeed, although the revolution had taken place in a predominantly Shia country, it showed that an Islamic revolution was applicable in the real world, and not just a theoretical utopia. Furthermore, as stated by Ghannouchi himself, “[t]he most important thing the Iranian revolution gave us was the idea of the conflict between the oppressed and the oppressors (bayn al-mustad’afin wa-l-mustakbirin), and that’s another translation of the conflict between the poor and the rich, the class struggle, but in an Islamist framework using Islamist terminology”¹⁴. Thus, the movement convened a congress during which it formally decided to become a political organization, giving itself a proper structure¹⁵.

In 1981, thanks to Prime Minister Mzali’s pluralist policy, the Jama’ah decided to reveal itself, under the new name of Movement for the Islamic Tendency (commonly known by its French acronym MTI). The MTI formally accepted the country’s democratic values and stated its intent to establish an Islamic state which would side with the oppressed members of society. Furthermore, it referred to its members as Islamists whom adhered to the Islamic tendency, operating an ideological differentiation between the Muslims who viewed politics through the prism of din-wa-dawla and those who didn’t¹⁶.

However, soon Bourguiba proved that his government’s pluralist policy was an illusion, and cracked down on the Islamists, seeing them as the greatest threat to his regime. This conflict brought the country to the brink of a civil war, especially after Ghannouchi was sentenced to life in prison, against Bourguiba’s wishes, as he wanted the founder of the MTI to be executed. This obsession caused Ben Ali, then-prime minister, to put in place a coup against Bourguiba, fearing that Ghannouchi’s execution would have only exacerbated the situation, making him a martyr (Perkins, 2014: 170-178). Nonetheless, Ben Ali’s regime, although initially promising, proved to be just as, if not even more, brutal than the previous one. Indeed, he opened to multiparty elections, for which the MTI, complying with a law that prohibited the use of religion by parties, changed its name to Harakat Al-Nahda (more commonly known as Ennahda). However, the party was still barred from participating in the 1989 elections, thus fielding its candidates as independents. The elections, whose outcome were a success for the Islamist candidates, pushed Ben Ali to repress the movement, placing many of its members under arrest, while many other, including Ghannouchi, opted for self-imposed exiles¹⁷.

¹³ Wolf, *Political Islam in Tunisia*, 42-44.

¹⁴ McCarthy, “When Islamist Lose”, 42.

¹⁵ The Islamist movement was forced to operate underground due to Tunisia’s strict party legislation, which had turned the country into a quasi-one-party state. Allani, “The Islamist in Tunisia”, 260.

¹⁶ McCarthy, “When Islamist Lose”, 43.

¹⁷ Torelli, *La Tunisia contemporanea*, 74-78.

While the situation for the Islamists in Tunisia was untenable, Ghannouchi became one of the most well recognized ideologues of political Islam, producing valuable works in which he specified the movement's theoretical system¹⁸. Whereas, during the better part of his stay in power, Ben Ali put in place a massive re-Islamisation of Tunisia's society, while maintaining Islam firmly under the government's control. Ben Ali's action was more akin to virtue-signalling than to a sincere appreciation for religion, seeing it as a means to defuse any sort of religion-based opposition to the regime, going to so far as to state that "only the State may provide for the flourishing [épanouissement] and spread [rayonnement] of Islam"¹⁹. This meant that any form of religiosity perceived by the state as provocative was cracked down upon, as for example the public use of the hijab, which was decried by Ben Ali as belonging to a violent form of Islam, as opposed to Tunisia's moderate Islam²⁰. Moreover, Ben Ali pseudo-Islamisation of Tunisia was put in place in response to the growing pressure coming from Gulf-based religious satellite channels, whom could have underlined, by contrast with their example, the then-current secularism of Tunisia²¹.

The years of repression and exile caused Ennahda to refine its goals and undertake a process of self-moderation²². This was caused not only by the brutal repression that the government perpetrated towards the party and its members, but also by the fact that the larger Tunisian population did not support it in its plight, as it did not share the party's more extreme positions. The final result of such moderation was the abandonment of the Islamic state project, which would be substituted by an ideological acceptance of democracy and the civil state. This new position was applied during the works for the constitutional draft following the uprisings of 2010-2011 which brought about the collapse of Ben Ali's regime²³.

Iran and the rise of post-Islamism

The death of Khomeini in 1989 and the simultaneous spread of globalization worldwide deeply influenced the rise of the post-Islamist discourse in Iran. As a matter of fact, globalization actively contributed to the development of suitable tools for questioning, and deconstructing as well, some by then antiquated Islamic practices and to elaborate policies more suited to current times. Moreover,

¹⁸ Tamimi, "Rashid Al-Gannoushi", passim.

¹⁹ Laurence, *Coping With Defeat*, 232-234.

²⁰ Haugbølle, "New Expressions of Islam", 326-327.

²¹ Haugbølle and Cavatorta, "Vive la grande famille", 102.

²² While fully aware of the debate over the appropriateness of the term 'moderation' and its derivatives, we have decided to use it to refer to a process of acceptance of democracy and pluralism as put in place by Ennahda. On the issue of moderation, specifically regarding Ennahda, see: Dikici Bilgin, "Revisiting the moderation controversy", 1507-1523; Netterstrøm, "After the Arab Spring", 110-124.

²³ Cavatorta and Merone, "Moderation Through Exclusion?", passim.

the social condition of Iranians, as well as the cultural and political distance between old and new generations, fostered the idea that only the Ummah could reform Islam so that it could not be the exclusive prerogative of the ruling classes²⁴.

The criticism around the idea of authority enhanced a public debate among both laic and religious ranks. The failure of Khatami's political design was determined by the specific will of the Supreme Leader and the neo-conservative front who abused their authority because of their interpretation of the *velayat-e faqih* doctrine, which incurred in substantial changes since 1989. A few months before his death, Khomeini issued a Constitutional revision, where the possession of the legal acknowledgement of *marja-e taqlid* to become Supreme Leader was abolished. Hence, those who could claim the title of *hojjatolleslam*, and therefore were not akin to be a source of emulation according to the Shiite doctrine, could become *rahbar*²⁵. The actual design of Khomeini was to extend the authority of the Supreme Leader to the regulation of the earthly life of the Ummah, whereas through the reinforcement of the religious institutions he aimed to safeguard the survival of the revolutionary political system²⁶. Hence, the dualism between political and religious power ceased to exist, and the Supreme Leader emerged as the only source of power²⁷. Eventually, if on the one hand Khomeini emerged as the unreachable *faqih* who was undoubtedly chosen by Allah, on the other hand his death revealed that no one could ever reach his authority.

The reframing process of power through the appointment of Khamenei was neither welcome among the entire Shiite hierarchy, nor among the population. The new Supreme Leader was believed to be weaker than his predecessor, mostly because his authority was not totally recognized. Hence, Khamenei gradually strengthened the political prerogatives of the religious institutions of the Republic, namely the Assembly of Experts, the Guardian Council, and the Expediency Council, and he revived the myth of the Holy Defence War against Iraq to reinforce the revolutionary discourse and gain the respect of the armed forces and the veterans. During the Nineties, the political design of the Supreme Leader came into contrast with the administrations of Rafsanjani and Khatami, that sought to rehabilitate Iran in the international arena through the pacific confrontation with globalization and the West²⁸. Therefore, Rafsanjani's presidency (1989-1997) fostered the rise of a political climate of discussion, where laic and religious intellectuals questioned themselves about the relationship between *fiqh* and the exercise of legislative and executive power. Hence, outstanding personalities such as Montazeri and his pupil Kadivar, and Soroush, contested the administration of

²⁴ Ehteshami, *Globalization and Geopolitics*, 130-143, 146-149.

²⁵ Constitution of the Islamic Republic of Iran, Articles 5, 107, 109.

²⁶ Arjomand, "Constitutional Implications", 247; Khomeini, *Sahifa-ye Nur*, 459-460.

²⁷ Boroujerdi and Rahimkani, *Postrevolutionary Iran*, 139-140.

²⁸ Ghabadzadeh, "Religious Secularity", 1005-1027.

power, and therefore of justice, and its architecture built by Khamenei²⁹. The outcome was the rise of the reformist movement led by Khatami, who openly challenged the Supreme Leader by asserting that the sclerotization of the Islamic political discourse, paired with an ultra-orthodox interpretation of the holy texts, provoked the rise of an autocracy and the neglect of social rights³⁰. According to Khatami, Allah gave human beings the ability to make choices, therefore the wellbeing of the Umma was a human responsibility. In other words, Khatami sided with Montazeri, Kadivar, and Soroush, and stressed the necessity of reforming the arrangement of power among the institutions of the Republic³¹.

During Ahmadinejad's administration, the neo-conservatist front and the Supreme Leader put an end to the reformist experience and vehemently reaffirmed the preeminence of the *velayat-e faqih* paradigm through the recovery of the dichotomy between Islam and the West, where Iranians were the oppressed (*mustazafin*) who need to engage a *jihad* against the Western world in order to preserve their integrity³². The redefinition of the Iranian political discourse, therefore, aimed to re-introduce a set of values typical of the Khomeinist period and to re-affirm the indisputable authority of religious institutions. Inevitably, the so-called 'talibanisation' of Iranian politics led to a strong opposition movement against Ahmadinejad and its authoritarian rule³³. During the first mandate of Ahmadinejad (2005-2009), political power was strongly held by religious institutions of the Islamic Republic. The strengthening of the triad formed by the Supreme Leader, the Guardian Council, and the Revolutionary Guards was indeed explicative of how the exercise of political power was intended to be, namely an orthodox political Islamism that was an exclusive prerogative of the neo-conservatist front³⁴. Nevertheless, the political discourse of the government turned into a sort of Islamic-Iranian nationalism, where Islam was regarded as an actual weapon against the West. In other words, the Orientalist dichotomy 'Islam vs. the West', as well as some cornerstones of Khomeinism such as the Holy Defence War or the understanding of *mustazafin*, were blended into a pretextual ideology that proved to be useful for the weakening of the representative institutions of the Islamic Republic³⁵. Eventually, Ahmadinejad accused the reformist intelligentsia of colluding with the Iran's greatest enemy, namely the United States, therefore erasing Khatami and his supporters from domestic policies³⁶. Due to the government's disregard for social rights and its abusive use of Islam for the

²⁹ Akhavi, "The Thought and the Role", 645-666; Siavoshi, *Montazeri*, passim; Kadivar, "The Theory of the State", passim; Bayat, *Making Islam Democratic*, 47-48; Soroush, Sadri and Sadri, *Reason*, 26-38.

³⁰ Vahdat, "Religious Modernity", 650-664.

³¹ Holliday, *Defining Iran*, 100-102; Vahdat, "Religious Modernity", 653-654.

³² Ansari, *Iran Under Ahmadinejad*, 23-40.

³³ Ehteshami and Zweiri, *Iran and the Rise of the Neoconservatives*, 92; Dabashi, *The Green Movement*, 51-64.

³⁴ Ansari, *Iran Under Ahmadinejad*, 23-40.

³⁵ Said, *Covering Islam*, 3-35; Ehteshami and Zweiri, *Iran and the Rise of the Neoconservatives*, 64-77.

³⁶ Ehteshami and Zweiri, *Iran and the Rise of the Neoconservatives*, 88; Rajaei, *Islamism and Modernism*, 172-180.

preservation of the authority of the Shiite conservative clergy, the youngest generations began to criticize political Islamism and its authority. The need to adjust and modernize Islam in accordance with historical, social and cultural circumstances was indeed crucial in laying the foundation for the spread of post-Islamism, which was intended as a sociopolitical movement accepted by most of Iranians. In other words, Ahmadinejad's first term was the perfect breeding ground for the quest for different political strategies through the recovery of transcendental Islamic practices in intellectual, social and political spheres³⁷. Basically, the need to create a different political environment where religious values must be respected and not exploited, and the establishment of pluralistic policies that could really guarantee a free political debate, led both to the spontaneous creation of a strong opposition front to the government and to the massive protests of the Green Movement in 2009³⁸. Iranian post-Islamism took its cue from the reframing of authority made by the Shiite hierarchy, and it was characterized by the need for purifying Islam from any potentially instrumental use. It is, in other words, a movement deeply rooted in the civil society that began to bloom in the second half of the Nineties thanks to the reformists and reached its peak with the Green Movement. Eventually, Iranian post-Islamism was a unique experiment among the Muslim panorama because it was not monolithic³⁹.

Between compromise and ideology: Ennahda's evolution

As anticipated, during his exile Ghannouchi formalized his theoretical system, producing valuable works. Among these there is *Public Liberties in the Islamic State*, wherein Ghannouchi argued the compatibility between Islam and democracy⁴⁰. His approach was extremely innovative, while still based on the Quran and the Sunna, and this attitude would inform the party's willingness to compromise during the constitutional process which followed Ben Ali's ousting.

During the National Constitutional Assembly's works, where Ennahda had a relative majority thanks to its success in the 2011 elections, the Islamists proved, though not without controversy, that they were willing to compromise on many fundamental issues, among these being the role of sharia in the constitution⁴¹.

In regard to the controversy surrounding the purported role of sharia in the Constitution, it must be noted that the party, having just reconstituted itself, had not yet defined its official position. Therefore, when it was decided to discuss it, a broader debate emerged among the Tunisian society, which was

³⁷ Bayat, *Making Islam Democratic*, 106-135.

³⁸ Ciftci, Wuthrich and Shamaileh, "Islam, Religious Outlooks", 438.

³⁹ Mahdavi, "Post-Islamist Trends", 95.

⁴⁰ Ghannouchi, *al-Hurriyat al-'Amma*, passim.

⁴¹ McCarthy, "When Islamists Lose", 374.

fearful of Ennahda's 'true' intentions. However, Ghannouchi had by then long been a proponent of a more nuanced interpretation of sharia, seeing it as a comprehensive way of life rather than as a strict rulebook. In fact, many, though not all, in the party agreed with this value-based approach to sharia, focusing more on the pursuit of its goals (*maqasid*), rather than just including a symbolic mention in the Constitution⁴². This does not mean that this position was not criticized, both within and without the party⁴³. However, Ghannouchi opined that: “[o]ur legislators should be imbued with the values of their religion even when they are in the process of enacting laws; at this point, they should need neither the guidance of the Ministry of Religious Affairs nor of the sharia scholars because these values are already embedded in them”⁴⁴. Therefore, as long as the country's majority was a Muslim one, the objectives of sharia would inevitably be pursued, due to the people's internalized values. This position is intertwined with Ghannouchi's belief that Islam and democracy are compatible, furthermore conceiving democracy, as a tool, as the best way to curb despotism in the Arab world⁴⁵. Ghannouchi's democratic stance can also be noted in his own nuanced conception of *ḥakimiyya*. As espoused by classical brands of political Islam, notably those that refer to Qutb's thought, *ḥakimiyya* is quite simply the fact that God is the legislator and sovereignty belongs to Him alone⁴⁶. However, Ghannouchi's understanding of *ḥakimiyya* was more refined. According to him it is unreasonable to think that God would personally exercise His rule over humankind, rather, any authority must derive from God. Consequently, the umma exercises sovereignty not in opposition to God, but as His deputy (*khalifa*)⁴⁷.

Yet, some of the compromises made during the constitutional process did mark an ideological departure from Ghannouchi's previous theoretical system, idealized in *Public Liberties in the Islamic State*. Foremost among these is the stance on apostasy and its criminalization. Indeed, Ghannouchi affirmed that: “[a]postasy is a crime [...] related to the preservation of Muslims and the structures of the Islamic state against enemy attacks [...]. It is a political crime comparable in other regimes to a crime of leaving by force the state's rule and attempting to destabilize it. It should be addressed using appropriate measures, proportionate to the importance and the danger that it represents”⁴⁸. However, due to the rising tensions following the assassinations of Belaid and Brahmi during the course of 2013, Ennahda's political legitimacy was waning. Then, when a member of the assembly belonging to Ennahda accused a secularist MP of having opposed Islam, his words were interpreted as a case of

⁴² Marks, *Convince, Coerce or Compromise?*, 20-22.

⁴³ Guazzone, “Ennahda Islamists”, 39.

⁴⁴ Ghannouchi, “The State and Religion”, 170.

⁴⁵ Jawad, “Democracy in Modern Islamic Thought”, 327.

⁴⁶ Campanini, *La politica nell'Islam*, 239.

⁴⁷ Santilli and Longo, “Tunisia”, 404.

⁴⁸ Netterstrøm, “After the Arab Spring”, 116.

takfir, precipitating the already precarious situation⁴⁹. Thus, the works of the Assembly were reopened in order to include the criminalization of takfir in the constitutional draft, as it eventually did in the sixth article⁵⁰. It should be noted that the criminalization of takfir was included in the same article which guaranteed the freedom of conscience and belief, which means not only the freedom of a person to choose their religion, but also to choose not to have one⁵¹. This fundamental ideological shift in Ennahda was preceded by an article authored by Ghannouchi, where, apart from supporting the compatibility between Islam and democracy and explaining Islam's relationship with the state, he affirmed that: "[...] [i]f there is agreement on the principle that there is no compulsion in religion, then I defended the principle of freedom in both directions: the freedom to join a religion and the freedom to leave it, because religiosity has no meaning when it is forced [...]"⁵².

In conclusion, Ennahda's stance during the constitutional process was one based on compromise, undoubtedly also to protect itself from possible persecutions, as those years saw the failure of the Islamist project in Egypt, which was halted by a military coup. Yet, Ennahda's compromises were part of a process of ideological evolution which began as a response to the repression put in place against it by the Ben Ali regime. It must also be noted that Ennahda and Ghannouchi based their ideological stance on their own interpretation of the Quran and Sunna. Indeed, Ghannouchi's belief in the compatibility between Islam and democracy rests chiefly on verse 256, surah 2, "no compulsion in religion", which, according to him, protects the most important freedom, that of belief⁵³. Similarly, the compromise on the issue of the criminalization of blasphemy, which Ennahda eventually yielded, was justified by its representatives in Sfax by quoting an example of caliph Omar as a precedent in support of a gradualist approach which aimed, in this case, at convincing, rather than coercing, the public to respect Islam⁵⁴.

After the constitutional draft was approved, on January 26, 2014, Ghannouchi authored an article which retraced the constitutional process, with its difficulties, and Ennahda's willingness to compromise in order to reach as broad a consensus as possible, as well as affirming that democracy had prevailed in Tunisia, with the help of Ennahda, and that: "[b]elieving in the positive power of Islam as an inspiration for the values of freedom and justice, Ennahda aimed at liberating society from political despotism, economic exploitation, social injustice and cultural stagnation or

⁴⁹ Hartshorn and Yadav, "(Re)Constituting Community", 9-10.

⁵⁰ Constitution of the Tunisian Republic, 2014: "The state is the guardian of religion. It guarantees freedom of conscience and belief, the free exercise of religious practices and the neutrality of mosques and places of worship from all partisan instrumentalisation. The state undertakes to disseminate the values of moderation and tolerance and the protection of the sacred, and the prohibition of all violations thereof. It undertakes equally to prohibit and fight against calls for Takfir and the incitement of violence and hatred". https://www.constituteproject.org/constitution/Tunisia_2014.pdf

⁵¹ Netterstrøm, "After the Arab Spring", 111.

⁵² Ghannouchi, "The State and Religion", 171.

⁵³ Tamimi, "Rashid Al-Gannoushi", 76.

⁵⁴ Marks, *Convince, Coerce or Compromise?*, 24.

dependence.”⁵⁵. Thus, in Ghannouchi’s opinion, Islam had indeed played a role in Tunisia’s constitutional process, but rather than assuming a strict juridical approach, Ennahda had preferred one based on values and morality.

This ideological evolution was finally acknowledged by the party and its cadres on Ennahda’s tenth Congress, which took place in May 2016. It was decided to ‘specialize’ the party, that is to say that the party would focus on politics, ceasing all moral activities and religious proselytes (*da’wa*), as well as officially renouncing its Islamist label, rather preferring to define itself as a ‘Muslim Democrat’ party, as, in Ghannouchi’s words: “the party no longer accepts the label of “Islamism” – a concept that has been disfigured in recent years by radical Islamists - as a description of its approach.”⁵⁶. Moreover, Ghannouchi affirmed that the separation between politics and religion would be among the party’s new objectives, stating that “[w]e believe that no political party can or should claim to represent religion and that the religious sphere should be managed by independent and neutral institutions. Put simply, religion should be nonpartisan.”⁵⁷. However, this position does not mean that the party had completely abandoned its religiousness, as can be noted by its new label, but also by the unwillingness of its members explain the specialization as a form of moderation, as Hasret Dikici Bilgin took note of their tendency to “de-emphasise the Islamist pedigree and instead underline that they respect religion and are religious, but that the party specialises in politics”⁵⁸. This can also be seen in the party’s new statute, which stemmed from the Congress and stresses the party’s focus on promoting Tunisia’s Arab and Islamic identity, as well as that of Ennahda⁵⁹.

The party congress had thus acknowledged a *fait accompli*, as in our opinion by that point Ennahda had entered a post-Islamist phase, based on its conduct during the constitutional process and its trend to reconcile Islam with democracy, doing so by changing its approach to the Islamist project, that is to say that it gave more importance to the protection of the values and rights derived from religion, rather than to a strict implementation of the laws and punishments derived from Islam. The concept of ‘Muslim democracy’, which can be summarized by Ghannouchi’s statement that “as Muslims, the values of Islam still guide our actions. However, we no longer consider the old ideological debates about Islamization or secularization of society to be necessary or even relevant”, in our opinion coincides with our understanding of post-Islamism⁶⁰.

It must be stressed, however, that inevitably Ennahda’s practice has sometimes been inconsistent with this ideology. This can be seen, in particular, in regard to the Ennahda-led government’s handling of

⁵⁵ Ghannouchi, “The Tunisian Experience”, 98.

⁵⁶ Meddeb, *Ennahda’s Uneasy Exit*, 2; Ghannouchi, “From Political Islam to Muslim Democracy”, 59.

⁵⁷ Ghannouchi, “From Political Islam to Muslim Democracy”, 63.

⁵⁸ Dikici Bilgin, “Revisiting the Moderation Controversy”, 7.

⁵⁹ See Al-Nizam Al-Siyasi, Ennahda political statute.

⁶⁰ Ghannouchi, “From Political Islam to Muslim Democracy”, 59.

the Salafi movement, Ansar al-Sharia (AST), between 2011 and 2013. Indeed, after a period of *laissez faire*, in which Ennahda hoped that the Salafis would moderate themselves, it was forced by circumstance to declare AST a terrorist organization and use a deeply flawed counterterrorism law which dated back to Ben Ali's regime and, ironically, had also been used against Ennahda members during the years of repression⁶¹. Nonetheless, it is inevitable for any party which is faced with the contingencies of government to sometimes put aside its ideology when no alternative is available.

A new understanding of Ali Shariati: neo-Shariatis' post-Islamism

Among the many shades of Iranian post-Islamism, namely the quasi-post-Islamist, the liberal post-Islamist and the neo-Shariati movement⁶², the very last one was indeed peculiar, since it recovered the thought of Ali Shariati to de-construct the Islamist discourse. The main exponents of the neo-Shariati movement were Ehsan, Sousan and Sara Shariati, the children of the late Ali, as well as Taqi Rahmani, and Hassan Yusefi-Eshkevari. Neo-Shariati's post-Islamist thought revolved around the idea that religion must be the instrument for the liberation of the oppressed, and not the tool for oppression. Hence, Ali Shariati's understanding of *mustazafin* was recovered and counterposed to the government's rhetoric, aiming to restore 'religious subjectivity' and 'social objectivity'⁶³. The legal responsibility of the government towards the civil society must coexist with the collective awareness of citizens as part of the Ummah in order to avoid the use of religion, economic power, and cultural justifications as exploitative tools for the survival of an authoritative regime. The dualism between oppressed and oppressor, typical of Ali Shariati's revolutionary discourse, was recovered with the intention of building a mutual bond of responsibility between the government and the people, where the former must guarantee the wellbeing of its community, and the latter had the duty to be aware of the government's conduct and avoid the oppression of the dominant class through religious, cultural and economic means⁶⁴. However, the neo-Shariati re-contextualized Ali Shariati's thought to current times, and they went beyond many political predictions of the late Ali⁶⁵.

A crucial aspect of the neo-Shariati's beliefs is the responsibility of the intellectuals toward the cultural and social development of society. Ehsan Shariati and Taghi Rahmani advocated for the essential role of grassroots movements in the establishment of a truly pluralistic civil society, since

⁶¹ Tamburini, "Anti-Terrorism Laws in the Maghreb Countries", 1246.

⁶² According to Mahdavi's classification, quasi-post-Islamism is intended as the reformist movement of the Nineties, embodied by Montazeri, Kadivar, and Khatami, and we identify Soroush as one of the main exponents of liberal post-Islamism. Mahdavi, "Post-Islamist Trends", 95.

⁶³ Shariati A, *Religion vs. Religion*, 43-63.

⁶⁴ Saffari, *Beyond Shariati*, 80-86.

⁶⁵ Shariati E, "Safar-e bozorg", 16-17.

without the presence of bottom-up organizations the State would never be participatory⁶⁶. The acknowledgement of the importance of civil society in the political life of the State was common in both Ali Shariati and neo-Shariati's discourses, agreeing on democracy as the best form of government for Iran. However, if Ali Shariati believed in the need for a "guided democracy" where intellectuals must be the avantgarde of citizens' claims, neo-Shariati instead preferred a "practice of democracy", where the role of the intellectuals should be the creation of a universal language of human rights⁶⁷. In that sense, neo-Shariati acknowledged representative democracy as the best form of government to ensure socio-political participation and the realization of the demands of the people in a broader sense⁶⁸. It was from these premises that the neo-Shariati insisted on the importance of democracy and how its secular nature could offer the chance to avert the Islamisation of the institutions of the Republic, whereas secularism *per se* was then intended to be the constraint against the instrumentalization of faith by the neo-conservative front⁶⁹.

According to Ehsan Shariati, the democratic form of government cannot allow for the exploitation of Islam by any kind of power, because if that happened the State would lose its spiritual values. Secularism would be the assurance of the neutrality of the Republic toward religious affairs, hence exalting the spirituality of Iran. Democracy could then become a weapon against the Islamization of the representative institutions of the Islamic Republic, since the secular nature of democracy could help recovering the actual meaning of spirituality and preserving the exploitation of Islam by those who detain political power⁷⁰. In other words, a secular democracy would protect the faith, and it would lead the Iranian umma to a path of freedom, equality and spirituality⁷¹. Also, democracy would be the realization of the safeguard of human rights of all those people who underwent anticolonial and domestic struggles against tyranny. In that sense, the neo-Shariati acknowledged the *aya* "There is no compulsion in faith" in accordance with the principles of *tawhid* and of *keramat-e ensani*, namely the human dignity, whose natural outcome was the universality of human rights⁷². Eventually, the existence of a public religion would be the actual demonstration of the force of the people's collective consciousness, and the intellectuals would perform their messianic role in speaking the universal language of human rights⁷³. The neo-Shariati believe that secularism allows for a clear

⁶⁶ Saffari, *Beyond Shariati*, 89; Mahdavi, "Post-Islamist Trends", 105.

⁶⁷ Shariati S, "Dar bareh shariaiet-e emkan-e moderniteh dini", 162; Ghamari-Tabrizi, "Contentious Public Religion", 512.

⁶⁸ Rahmani, "Azadi dar marhaleh eradeh", 31.

⁶⁹ Yousefi, *Religion and Revolution in the Modern World*, 73-93; Saffari, *Beyond Shariati*, 88-89.

⁷⁰ Shariati E, "Safar-e bozorg", *passim*.

⁷¹ Shariati E, "Safar-e bozorg", 16-17; Shariati E, "Hamchenan armangara".

⁷² Quran, II: 256.

⁷³ Saffari, *Beyond Shariati*, 91.

separation between the realm of ideologies and the realm of governance, so that the State can remain a neutral institution and the public religion would ease the protection of the rights of the umma⁷⁴.

The universality of human rights was also crucial in avoiding the risks of nativism or cultural essentialism. As a matter of fact, the instrumental use of the martyrs of the Holy Defence War was exploited many times by the Shiite hierarchy to protect their prerogatives, simultaneously strengthening the religious foundations of the State by imposing a theocratic interpretation of sharia. The outcome was the creation of a nativist-Islamic political discourse, which other than being outdated in regard to current times was also extremely conservative and implied a very restrictive understanding of rights in accordance to the Islamic law. The neo-Shariati criticized the absolute mandate of the Islamic jurist, since it curbed *fiqh* to a deterministic and eternal universe that was indeed functional to the survival of a theocratic regime. Therefore, they proposed instead an historical approach to Islamic values, where the separation between religious and political power would be crucial in introducing secularism as the instrument for the observance of human rights⁷⁵.

Ennahda and the neo-Shariati: Islam, democracy, post-Islamism

The cases of Ennahda and the neo-Shariati highlight different shades of post-Islamism, mainly due to the different contexts where they emerged. The two case studies can in fact be compared on the basis of three features, namely the relationship between Islam and democracy, the recognition of rights, and the historical, political and institutional developments which have influenced their evolution.

Both Ennahda and the neo-Shariati dealt with the compatibility between Islam and democracy, even though the contexts in which they developed this concept were different and they had different outcomes. Ennahda's conception of the compatibility was initially meant as the basis for the creation of an Islamic state in Tunisia, however the party's ideological evolution brought it to reject the Islamist label, adopting as one of its goals the protection of religion from any sort of political exploitation. Although in its early stages the Tunisian Islamic movement's aim was that of creating an Islamic state in Tunisia, Ennahda's position has long since abandoned such proposition. In fact, since the Nineties Ghannouchi has proposed that Islam and democracy are fully compatible, initially with the intent of idealizing an Islamic state that would be democratic. However, as seen after the regime change in Tunisia, Ennahda has come to the conclusion that among the systems available, the democratic one is the most suited to avoid the emergence of authoritarian regimes, and allows for

⁷⁴ Shariati E, "Hamchenan armangara".

⁷⁵ Alijani, "Pre-Secular Iranians", 31.

religion to flourish. Furthermore, the party, through its evolution, has adopted a stance aimed at freeing religion from politics, believing that no single political actor should be able to represent religion. This can also be noted in Tunisia's 2014 constitution, where the state is defined as 'civil', although indeed Islam is its religion. Thus, the state that emerged with Ennahda's participation does have a religious aspect, but more in a cultural sense than in a juridical one. Indeed, Ennahda itself, in adopting the label of 'Muslim Democracy', conceived religion as a cultural aspect of the party, thus officially abandoning any religious activity as well as its previous Islamist label.

On the other hand, the neo-Shariati considered democracy as a true weapon against any possible political exploitation of Islam. Democracy is in fact pivotal in the understanding of post-Islamism made by the neo-Shariati. The acknowledgement of civil society and grassroots movements as the foundation of a pluralistic State led the neo-Shariati to focus on the importance of the respect of the demands of the citizens. In that sense, representative democracy was intended to be the best form of government for Iran because of its secularist nature. Not only Islam and democracy are compatible with each other, but secularism can also become the most useful tool to avoid the Islamization of the institutions of the State. Therefore, the "practice of democracy", as intended by the neo-Shariati, implied the defense of Islam from any possible exploitation from those who are in power, namely the triad formed by the Supreme Leader, the Guardian Council, and the Revolutionary Guards. The conception of the State made by the neo-Shariati inevitably excluded religion from the government but did not imply the removal of Islam from Iranian society.

Concerning political rights, both Ennahda and the neo-Shariati moved from the *aya* 256 of Surat al-Baqarah, which states that "there is no compulsion in religion". Therefore, this *aya* represents the basis for the conception of human rights in relation to dignity in both movements. As we have seen, through its ideological evolution Ennahda has come to favour an approach based on the protection of rights rather than the imposition of norms. Indeed, this position hails back to the Nineties, when Ghannouchi focused on strengthening the party's theoretical system, but it was fully explicated during the Constitutional process, with the abandonment of the request for the inclusion of sharia in the constitution, preferring instead to focus on its values. Moreover, regarding human rights, Ennahda and Ghannouchi have shown a high degree of acceptance towards rights such as that of conscience and the right to leave one's religion, which serves to show their acceptance of pluralism. Indeed, Ghannouchi himself has long been a proponent of the position that Islam represents the first historical instance of the affirmation of human rights and dignity, in particular those of freedom and equality, which only later were expressed in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights⁷⁶.

⁷⁶ Tamimi, "Rashid Al-Gannoushi", 97.

The discourse on human and political rights is indeed one of the main features of neo-Shariati post-Islamism. According to them, the implementation of a true egalitarian and pluralistic society was deeply connected to the cultural and social development of the Iranian people, where grassroots movements and intellectuals played a crucial role. Neo-Shariati put emphasis onto the importance of the acknowledgement of rights differently from the institutions of the Islamic Republic, therefore advocating the need for the separation between religion and governance. Hence, their purpose was to establish a universalist discourse on human rights through a collective awakening and a renewed consciousness of the people⁷⁷. Faith, indeed, was fundamental in the framework of the safeguard of human rights, because it guaranteed the respect of human dignity. Therefore, neo-Shariati identify a mutual responsibility between the civil society and the institutions in the protection of the neutrality of the State and of the pureness of faith, so that the exploitation of Islam in oppressive terms can be avoided.

One of the main differences between Ennahda and the neo-Shariati can be found in the different contexts where they emerged, whose political and institutional developments influenced the evolution of these two movements, as well as the form they took. In particular, Ennahda was able to constitute itself as a political party akin to Western mass parties, but with Islamist specificities such as the *Majlis Al Shura*, whereas the neo-Shariati were never admitted to public political life. Whereas Ennahda was forced to develop its ideology in response to the repressions put in place by Bourguiba and especially Ben Ali, the neo-Shariati benefited from Khatami's reformist agenda during which they were able to strengthen their political discourse. Ennahda's ideological evolution has stemmed from a process of introspection, but it has also been influenced by pragmatic factors. Indeed, the severe repression it faced during Ben Ali's regime has played a crucial role in such a process. Moreover, even during the constitutional process external events have reinforced its commitment to compromise, as the party feared a counterrevolution similar to that which ended the Islamist experience in Egypt, or similarly in Algeria. This attitude to compromise brought Ennahda to form a coalition government with the secularist party *Nida Tunus* after the 2014 elections, where Ennahda placed second. Indeed, we can assume that the party's experience in governing the country, both as the senior (2011-2014) and as the junior member of government after the 2014 elections, has played a role in its evolution towards a more political focus vis-à-vis a religious one, as reaffirmed during the 2016 Congress. The neo-Shariati, on the other hand, were able to develop their political discourse during politically fertile times. Khatami's presidency launched a reformist agenda that aimed to establish an Islamic democracy, therefore enhancing debates among intellectuals about the relationship between Islam and democracy. Since that topic was nothing new among the Iranian

⁷⁷ Saffari, *Beyond Shariati*, 91.

intelligentsia since the Sixties, the neo-Shariati recovered and modernized Shariati's thought with the demands of the time. However, differently from Ennahda, the neo-Shariati never experienced an electoral victory, mainly because they never constituted a political party, but they were hit by the repression of the Islamic Republic during the Green Movement and in its aftermath.

Conclusions

The cases of Ennahda and the neo-Shariati represent two peculiar experiences of post-Islamism. Even though Ennahda's evolution was strongly influenced and possibly driven by the repression against it from the Tunisian regimes, while the neo-Shariati enjoyed the reformist era of the Islamic Republic, therefore a time of relative political openness and inclusion, they both converged on their objective being the protection of Islam from any kind of political exploitation. Clearly, in Ennahda's case this came after a long process of introspection which brought it from being an Islamist movement to a Muslim Democratic Party, equatable to a post-Islamist one, even though they reject such label. The neo-Shariati too came after a period of introspection, but it was mainly directed at the reinterpretation and evolution of Ali Shariati's thought, and a critique of Islamism as intended by the Shiite institutions. In that sense, it can be argued that post-Islamism developed in Tunisia within the Islamist movement itself, whereas in Iran it was closer to a theoretical-political debate and it was characterized as a form of opposition against the institutions of the Islamic Republic.

Notwithstanding the peculiarity of their experiences, both Tunisia and Iran experienced the persistence of a sharp division between public and private space, which influenced the political parties' and movements' interest in democracy. Since the public space was subjected to the rules of the regime, the private space became the actual sphere of political expression because it eluded governmental control. The theoretical debate about post-Islamism and Islamism in Tunisia and Iran was indeed comparable because, even if arising from different paths, in both cases it could represent a possible disturbance to the ruling élite. In other words, since it was impossible to develop a collective political discourse on post-Islamism and Islamism in the public space, Ennahda and the neo-Shariati took shelter in the private space. Both Ennahda and the neo-Shariati converge on the belief that rights are an intrinsic aspect of Islam, thus making the latter fully compatible with democracy. The centrality of rights as derived from the Islamic understanding of human dignity is fundamental in labeling these movements as post-Islamist and, no matter the differences, it allows for a comparison between different conceptions of Islam as the Sunni and the Shia one.

Even if the renewed attention to human rights was indeed crucial in paving the way for post-Islamism, the latter was also strongly tied to the understanding of both secularism and Islamism in Tunisia and

Iran. Even though clearly opposite, Tunisian secularism and Iranian Islamism presented a common feature, namely the relationship between structural and subjective agency of the regimes enabling those policies. Both the secular and the Islamist governments, in fact, proved to be efficient only at a structural level, mainly enforcing specific legislations for the achievement of their goals. The population in its entirety, in both cases, was not subjectively involved because it did not identify in the regime's beliefs. It is indeed true that in the case of an Islamic regime detecting possible post-Islamist trends can be easier than in a secular state, as proved by the neo-Shariati case. Whenever a secular regime belonging to the Muslim world enforces the separation between religion and state, an Islamist response is often inevitable, even if it is not destined to maintain its initial ideology. In that sense, the case of Ennahda is particularly interesting, because it managed to adapt itself to the current political debates, without however losing its prerogatives. The cases of the neo-Shariati and Ennahda, eventually, prove that post-Islamism is neither just a social discourse on the compatibility between Islam and democracy, nor just a political output of circumstances. Post-Islamism shows its own specificities, influenced by the geographical and historical conditions, as asserted by Bayat, and each post-Islamist experience can differ from the other. However, thanks to these differences and the comparison between them, it is possible to broaden our understanding of post-Islamist discourse and the way it changes based on the contexts where it develops, while maintaining its basic features.

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